

Effect of Instructional Simulation Strategy On Learning Outcomes of Secondary School Students in Biology in Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract:

The study examined the effect of instructional simulation strategy on learning outcomes of secondary school students in Biology in Ondo State, Nigeria. The study adopted quasi – experimental pre-test and post-test two group design (experimental group and control group) research design. The targeted population for the study consisted of all the Senior Secondary School (S.S.S.) one students in public secondary schools in Ondo State. The sample consisted of 134 S.S.S. 1 students (class intact size) drawn from six public secondary schools in Ondo State. The sample was selected using multistage sampling procedure. Two research instruments namely Biology Achievement Test (BAT) and Questionnaire on Students' Interest in Biology (QSIB) were used to collect relevant data for this study. The face and content validity of the instruments were ensured by experts in Tests and Measurement and Biology Education. The reliability of the instruments was established using internal consistency method which yielded reliability co-efficient values of 0.74 and 0.78 for BAT and QSIB respectively. The data collected for this study were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The findings of the study revealed that the two groups (instructional simulation strategy and conventional method) were homogeneous at the commencement of the experiment. The

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use of instructional simulation strategy and conventional method enhanced performance and interest of students in Biology while instructional simulation strategy is the more effective. It was recommended among others that the use of instructional simulation strategy should be encouraged in Biology class in secondary schools so as to enhance better academic performance and interest of students in Biology.

Keywords: Instructional Simulation Strategy, Learning Outcomes, Biology, Students,

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Introduction

One of the aims of Science Education is to improve students' interest in Science subjects. Biology, to be precise is central to many of the scientific areas of human endeavours and its teaching should be given a serious attention. Biology is the science which studies living things and concerns itself with the study of the structure, behaviour, distribution, the origin of plants and animals and their bond with their environments.

Biology is done at the Senior Secondary School (senior secondary one (S.S.S 1) to senior secondary three (S.S.S 3) classes) as a sole subject. This group of students at Junior Secondary School (J.S.S 1 – 3) had done Integrated Science which is aimed at preparing them for doing Biology at the Senior Secondary level. It has been detected that Biology is a welcome science subject among senior secondary school students because it has less mathematical calculations unlike Physics and Chemistry hence, has a very high enrolment of students in the external examination (Senior School Certificate Examination) more than Physics and Chemistry. It is also a well-known subject for prospective medical, engineering and agricultural students.

The Senior Secondary School Biology results of Ondo state from 2010 and 2019 were generally poor and deplorable over the years as revealed by the analysis of students' performance at the SSCE in the following table.

Statistical Data of WAEC Performance of Secondary School Students in Biology for the Year 2010-2019

Exam Year	No of Registered Students			% passed A1 – C6	% failed D7 – F9
	Total	M	F		
2010	9683	4934	4749	35	65
2011	11144	5012	5532	32	68
2012	9239	4560	4679	39	61
2013	9043	4374	4669	29	71
2014	9829	4897	4932	35	65
2015	10072	4858	5214	39	61
2016	9189	4495	4694	43	57
2017	9258	4347	4911	44	56
2018	9312	4456	4856	42	58
2019	10141	4689	5452	46	54

Source: Ondo State Ministry of Education.

The report clearly displayed that the percentage of candidates that passed Biology at credit level and above in Ondo State was below 45%. One of the major and leading factors for poor performance in Biology examination by students is linked to the use of conservative method in the teaching of Biology in secondary school. Despite the recommendations for use of innovative methods for teaching and learning science by the Federal Ministry of Education's 6-3-3-4 curriculum reform, and suggestions by many Science Educators, reports from educators and researchers indicated that students' performance in Biology is still very poor. The poor performance of Biology students has been linked with the use of poor methods of teaching and lack of interest

The quest to restrain the inadequacies of the conventional method used in teaching and learning of Biology led to the discovery of other innovative teaching methods, such as, the concept mappings, instructional simulation, blended learning, simulations and games, spaced-learning, inquiry method, problem based learning among others (Opara, 2011). These innovative methods are considered as effective teaching methods that can increase students' performance and interest in Biology. One of the developing methods is instructional simulation strategy.

Simulation is considered as a representation of the behaviour or characteristics of a system through the use of another outlet specially a computer programme designed for the purpose (Krulik, 2010). Simulation is an instrument that enables learning through representation and practice in a repeatable, focused environment (Awodun, 2010). Simulation means imitation of situation. Simulation is otherwise known as 'the act of pretending or deception'. Simulation involves the use of model- a simplified version of authenticity which reduces the intricacy of a real-life situation, taking from reality only those important features of the learning objectives (Awodun, 2010).

It can mean making replicas or representations of machines for demonstration or analysis of difficulties but clearly illustrates real life or hypothetical situations. Simulation is used with the assistance of computer to simplify real life situation (simulation) and this could aid to manage the class, support unwilling learners, arouse gifted children and ease administration.

Simulations are instruments that enable learning through representation and practice in a repeatable, focused environment. It aids students to identify and understand factors which control the system and or forecast the future behaviour of a system. It can also bring into the classroom situation, aspects of the world or universe that are too luxurious, dangerous, abstract, difficult or too slow or too fast in occurrence to be comprehended. The use of simulations in the teaching and learning of Biology could help the understanding of abstract and difficult concepts by allowing students to develop their own understanding. As observed by Umoke and Nwafor (2014) , that the use of simulations to teach science gives encouraging results over time and permits the learner to manipulate variables or parameters and then observe the consequences of their actions.

Instructional simulation includes instructional elements that help a learner discover, navigate or obtain more information about that environment that cannot generally be attained from mere experimentation. (Eskrootchi & Oskrochi, 2010), views that Instructional simulations combine visual and interactive learning experiences, promotes application of knowledge, and provides a simplified representation of real world system.

The integration of instructional simulation in Biology classrooms can offer an effective learning environment for students to improve their Biology skills by engaging them with "real world" conditions to make the abstract concepts concrete and clear. In this way students could have a meaningful and retaining learning and they will be much more ready for their future education life such as university education or their proficient life. The instructional simulation environment offers a platform to apply the knowledge in a given situation and their interactions results in the finding of new knowledge that will help cognitive domain development and the accumulation of knowledge (Sharma, 2011).

If Biology performances generally continue to be poor as it is now, Ondo State may never attain her goal of emerging modern technology using her own human resources. Ondo State, being an agricultural state with many rural settlements and communities needs to have an innovative educational system that will arouse the teaching and learning of science so that the state would be able to produce capable Scientists, Science Educators, Medical, Agricultural and other professionals. The study therefore examined the effect of instructional simulation strategy on learning outcomes of secondary school students in Biology in Ondo State, Nigeria. The study specifically examined:

- i. the effects of instructional simulation strategy and conventional method on the academic performance of students in Biology; and
- ii. the effect of instructional simulation strategy in eliciting students' interest in Biology.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What are the effects of instructional simulation strategy and conventional method on the academic performance of students in Biology?
2. What is the effect of instructional simulation strategy in eliciting students' interest in Biology?

Research Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses were generated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the pre-test mean score of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method
2. There is no significant difference in the interest of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method before treatment
3. There is no significant difference in the post-test mean score of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method
4. There is no significant difference in the interest of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method after treatment

Methodology

The study adopted quasi – experimental pre-test and post-test two group design (experimental group and control group) research design. The targeted population for the study consisted of all the Senior Secondary School (S.S.S.) one students in public secondary schools in Ondo State. The sample consisted of 134 S.S.S. 1 students (class intact size) drawn from six public secondary schools in Ondo State. The sample was selected using multistage sampling procedure.

Two research instruments namely Biology Achievement Test (BAT) and Questionnaire on Students' Interest in Biology (QSIB) were used to collect relevant data for this study. BAT was self-designed by the researcher and measured students' academic performance in Biology. It consisted of sections A and B. Section A sought for the bio-data of the respondents while Section B consisted of 20 objectives items with four options. Questionnaire on Students' Interest in Biology (QSIB) both consisted of sections A and B. Section A sought for bio-data of the respondents while section B of both instruments consisted of 30 items which sought for students' interest towards Biology.

The face and content validity of the instruments were ensured by experts in Tests and Measurement and Biology Education. The reliability of the instruments was established using internal consistency method which yielded reliability co-efficient values of 0.74 and 0.78 for BAT and QSIB respectively. These values were considered high enough to make the instruments adequate for use. Thus the instruments were considered reliable and suitable for the study. The study was carried out in three phases namely pre-treatment, treatment and post treatment Stage. The data collected for this study were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were answered using means and standard deviation. All the hypotheses were tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Question 1: What are the effects of instructional simulation strategy and conventional method on the academic performance of students in Biology?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of pre-test and post-test scores of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method

Strategies	Test	N	Mean	S.D	Mean Diff.
Instructional simulation strategy	Pre Test	74	4.69	1.45	11.30
	Post Test		15.99	0.82	
Conventional	Pre Test	60	4.85	0.73	6.15
	Post Test		11.00	1.53	
Total		134			

From Table 1, it is shown that the mean difference in students' performance in Biology between pre-test and post-test scores for instructional simulation strategy is 11.30 and conventional method is 6.15. It appears that the use of instructional simulation strategy and conventional method influences students' performance in Biology with instructional simulation strategy being the more effective method in the teaching of Biology. The graphical representation below further shows the more effective method in the teaching of Biology.

Figure i: Pre-test and Post-test mean scores of students exposed to Instructional simulation strategy and Conventional method

Question 2: What is the effect of instructional simulation strategy in eliciting students’ interest in Biology?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation of effect of Instructional simulation strategy in eliciting students’ interest in Biology

Strategy	Test	N	Mean	S.D	Mean Diff.
Instructional simulation strategy	Before Treatment	74	69.20	1.24	39.30
	After Treatment		108.50	1.90	
Total		74			

Table 3 shows the mean pre-treatment and mean post-treatment scores of interest of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy. The mean pre-treatment score of interest of students is 69.20 while mean post-treatment score of interest of students is 108.50. The table above shows that the mean difference in students’ interest in Biology between pre-treatment and post-treatment scores for instructional simulation strategy is 39.30. The graphical representation below further shows the effect of instructional simulation strategy in eliciting students’ interest in Biology.

Figure ii: Bar chart showing effect of Instructional simulation strategy in eliciting students' interest in Biology

Testing of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the pre-test mean score of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method

Table 3: t-test analysis for difference in the pre-test mean score of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P
Instructional simulation strategy	74	4.69	0.76	132	1.224	0.223
Conventional	60	4.85	0.73			

P>0.05

Table 3 shows that the t-cal value of 1.224 is not significant because the P value (0.223) > 0.05. This implies that null hypothesis is not rejected. Hence, there is no significant difference in the pre-test mean score of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method. The students in the groups are homogeneous at the commencement of the study.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the interest of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method before treatment

Table 4: t-test analysis for difference in the interest of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method before treatment

Variations	N	Mean	SD	Df	t _{cal}	P
Instructional simulation strategy	74	69.20	1.24	132	1.222	0.224
Conventional	60	68.98	0.70			

P>0.05

Table 4 shows that the t-cal value of 1.222 is not significant because the P value (0.224) > 0.05. This implies that null hypothesis is not rejected. Hence, there is no significant

difference in the interest of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method before treatment.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant difference in the post-test mean score of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method

Table 5: t-test analysis for difference in the post-test mean score of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P
Instructional simulation strategy	74	15.99	0.82	132	24.117	0.000*
Conventional	60	11.00	1.53			

*P<0.05

Table 5 shows that the t-cal value of 24.117 is significant because the P value (0.000) < 0.05. This implies that null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is significant difference in the post-test mean score of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method. The mean score showed a significant difference of 4.99 in favour of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy.

Hypothesis 4: There is no significant difference in the interest of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method after treatment

Table 6: t-test analysis for difference in the interest of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method after treatment

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P
Instructional simulation strategy	74	108.50	1.90	132	37.950	0.000*
Conventional	60	90.42	3.51			

*P<0.05

Table 6 shows that the t-cal value of 37.950 is significant because the P value (0.000) < 0.05. This implies that null hypothesis is rejected. Hence, there is significant difference in the interest of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method after treatment. The mean score showed a significant difference of 18.08 in favour of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy. Students exposed to instructional simulation strategy showed more interest to learning of Biology than those in the conventional group.

Discussion

The study revealed that there was no significant difference in the pre-test mean score and interest of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method. The performance and interest of students in both experimental and control groups were low and do not differ statistically. This finding established the homogeneity of the two groups involved in the study prior to the experiment. In other words, it could be said that the knowledge baseline and interest for the two groups involved in the study are equal.

The study revealed that there was significant difference in the post-test mean score of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method. There was a better improvement in the performance of students resulting from their exposure to instructional simulation strategy. This implies that the introduction of instructional

simulation strategy to the experimental group made them to perform better than the control group that was not exposed to treatment. This study agrees with the findings of Umoke and Nwafor (2014) that the effective and efficient use of instructional simulation strategy enhances students' academic performance in Biology. The findings also agree with Chauham (2009) and Benson (2011) that instructional simulation strategy application yielded better results than the conventional method because, it gives flexibility for students' learning in terms of learning style and study time, it improves students' experience and enhances their engagement. Also, the study is in line with the assertions of Olofin (2019) that are of the opinion that the use of good teaching strategies has the potency to improve cognition of students hence; it justifies the postulate of this study that instructional simulation strategy could enhance the performance of students in Biology.

The findings of this study revealed significant difference in the interest of students exposed to instructional simulation strategy and conventional method after treatment. Students exposed to instructional simulation strategy showed more interest to learning of Biology than those in the conventional group because, it integrates the use of face to face and demonstration which facilitates proper assimilation and comprehension. This study is in conformity with the findings of Rising (2009) and Olofin (2019) that the use of appropriate teaching techniques by teacher during the teaching-learning process enhances students' interest and performance.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it could be concluded that, the two groups (instructional simulation strategy and conventional method) were homogeneous at the commencement of the experiment. The use of instructional simulation strategy and conventional method enhanced performance and interest of students in Biology while instructional simulation strategy is the more effective.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made;

1. The use of instructional simulation strategy should be encouraged in Biology class in secondary schools so as to enhance better academic performance and interest of students in Biology.
2. Biology teachers should be trained on the use of facilities and equipment needed for instructional simulation in the classroom.
3. Teachers should manage the time allocated well on time-table to accommodate the use of instructional simulation strategy in the classroom

References

- Awodun, A.O. (2010). *Evaluation of PowerPoint presentation effectiveness on teaching of motion on students' academic performance in Physics at secondary school level*. Unpublished Masters Degree thesis in Science Education, Faculty of Education, University of Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.
- Benson A.A. (2011). Effects of Multimedia Instruction on Senior Secondary School Students' Achievement in Physics. *European Journal of Educational Studies*, 3(3), 537 – 548
- Chauham, J. (2009). A study of the simulation learning and retention of materials presented lecture and by silent film. *Journal of Educational Research*, 38, (1). 47 – 58.
- Eskrootchi, R., & Oskrochi, G. R. (2010). A Study of The Efficacy of Project-Based Learning Integrated with Computer-Based Simulation-STELLA. *Educational Technology and Society*, 13(1), 236–245.
- Krulik, R.N. (2010). *A Practical Approach to Problem Solving*. New York: The Macmillan.
- Olofin, S. O. (2019). Effects of Kolawole's Problem-Solving strategy and teachers' characteristics on the academic performance of secondary school students in Mathematics in Nigeria. Unpublished Ph.D Thesis, Department of Science Education, Ekiti State University
- Opara, J. A. (2011). Inquiry Method and Students' Academic Achievement in Biology: Lessons and Policy Implications: *American-Eurasian Journal of Scientific Research*, 6 (1), 28-31.
- Rising, A. (2009). The implications of ICT and simulation for science teaching: Wither Nigeria. *Complex Systems Publication Inc.* 17(1), 113-124
- Sharma, R. (2011), 'Barriers in Using Technology for Education in Developing Countries', IEEE0-7803-7724-9103.Singapore schools', *Computers & Education* 41(1), 49--63.
- Umoke, J. C., and Nwafor, C. C. (2014). Effects of Instructional Simulation on Secondary School Students' Achievement in Biology. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 5(19), 101-110.

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